

Teaching and Learning Strategies in 21st century

*Mr. Bandgar Vilas Bhanudas,
Mr. Bagwan jakir salauddin*

Teaching is an interaction process, interaction means participation of teacher, student and both are benefited by this the interaction takes place for achieving desired Objectives. Teaching is relationship which is established between three focal points in education (teacher, student and subject) .Teaching Strategies play a vital role in education system when they are implemented in system that encourage collaboration among staff, students and in which each is a part of a well planned whole teacher should plan short term and long term Strategies according to student and teaching methods is part of Strategies, Student enable to know value education, Life skill education by Strategies used by teacher which help them in meaning a valuable person of India output teaching learning process is depending upon teaching Strategies it is the core elements of education system.

Key words: interaction process, achieving, collaboration, teaching methods etc

Introduction:

In teaching learning process teachers, students used many methods, techniques and strategies in daily teaching, learning, and process, there are many methods e.g. lecture discussion, inductive, deductive etc. But in this modern era of education There are many new methods, techniques are invented by educations teaching, learning strategies are the thoughts of actions that individual use to accomplish learning all strategies are effective and helping to acquire successful knowledge and improve students' performance a student centered approach which actively engages the young person.

Some of learning strategies that could be incorporated in a comprehensive approach included self-directed learning, Co. operating learning, role playing model, peace deduction and parent involvement.

Strategies are most successful when they are implements in a system that encourages collaboration among staff and students and in which each is a part of a well-planned whole education system. Strategies are most effective when they are applied in positive, supportive environment, where there is recognition of the emotional, social of psychical needs of students and where individual strengths are recognized natured and developed.

Strategies:

Teaching learning strategies helps to develop listening verbal communication, critical thinking and decision making power skills in the classroom context. Teaching learning strategies that motivates student and increase students retention by creating opportunities for students to see, hear says and do Malcolm Knowles effective when if moves practically, relevance respect etc. instructors who understand and accept these guiding principles will greatly enhance the learning experience of their students

Using teaching learning strategies:

The teaching of learning strategies are used to engage student. Teachers should refer to before planning of the resource for an explanation of the purpose and how to implement the strategy with their class.

1. Co-Operative Learning Co- Operative learning is strategies one of the best research of all teaching. The result show that student who have opportunities to work collaboratively, learning faster and more efficiently, have grater retention and

fell move positive about learning experience. In this Co-Operative learning both teacher and students are aware of the teaching learning process. Co-Operative learning means learning with group it is a way for students to learn essential interpersonal life skill and to develop the ability to work collaboratively. A skill now greatly in demand in the work place. It is a way for students to take turns with different roles such as facilitator, reporter, recorder etc.

Objective of co. operative learning strategies:

1. To work collaboratively.
2. To learn faster and efficiently.
3. To have grater recantation.
4. To work with group.
5. To develop interpersonal life skill.

2. Active learning strategies:

Mayers and jones (1993) define 'Active learning as learning environments that'

Allow " Students to talk and listen, read write and reflect as the approach course content through problem soluingexercise, informal small group, simulation case studies, role playing and other all of which require student to apply what they are learning many studies show that learning is enhanced when students become actively involved in the learning process.

Instructional strategies that engage students in the learning process, stimulate critical thinking and greater awareness of other perspectives, all at though there are times when lecturing is the most appropriate method for disseminating information current thinking in college teaching learning suggests that the use of a variety of instructional strategies can positively enhance students learning obviously,

teaching strategies should be carefully matched to the learning objectives of a particular lesson.

Objectives Active learning strategies:

- 1] To develop confidence of the students.
- 2] To active participation of the students
- 3] To make students active in learning.

3. Ict enabled flexible teaching learning strategies:

This strategy enables the learner to choose the content, media and the method of learning as per one's own requirement and gets considerable scope for interaction with the tutors and fellow learners. This includes.

- 1] Virtual learning environment
- 2] G-Mobile Technology.
- 3] Blended learning (convergence of traditional teaching and learning method)

4. Thinking skills strategies:

Thinking skills strategies are teaching learning strategies that strive to improve achievements by consciously developed students ability to consider ideas, analyze perspectives solve problem and make decisions. In this sense all teaching learning instructions strategies could be considered thinking skills strategies. However it is use full to focus on those strategies that develop thinking directly from lower to higher order (e.g. bloom's knowledge synthesis)

- 1] Brian storming.
- 2] Concept mapping
- 3] Experimenting
- 4] Mind map etc.

Conclusion:

By using co. operative learning in the learning process the teaching and learning becomes effective the student get the freedom for their own thinking power, imagination power, evaluation, collecting information analysis of data, synthesis and knowledge construction as like co. operative learning keeping fit for learning is different. A teacher can give psychologically treatment to the student class and made the environment mentally and physically healthy.

References:

Buehl, D. (1995). Classroom strategies for interactive learning schofield. WI Wisconsin state reading association.

Alan, Crowfod (2005). Teaching and learning strategic for the thinking classroom, new yeark, ivy. International debate Edu. Association publication.

Ally n and bacon (1990). Active learning 101 strategies to teach any subject. Heinemama Publication.

E-Reference :

<http://www.det.wa.edu.qu>.

<http://www.gum.edu/strategy.htm>.

<http://timquntely.blogspot.com>